

AXIOMATIC MODELS OF ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

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Abstract. *One of the priority areas in education at present is informatization. In this regard, the search for methodological support that contributes to the organization of educational and professional activities with the usage of information and communication technologies seems to be an urgent task. Didactic possibilities of modern information and communication technologies contribute to the intensification and improvement of the educational process. At the same time, electronic educational resources used as educational, methodological, organizational, informational, reference and other means of information and communication technologies became particularly important. They allow forming the methodological support of the implemented disciplines in the conditions of the real educational process in the system of higher and secondary vocational education. The article substantiates the possibility of using axiomatic models for the development of electronic educational resources by formalizing the didactic content of the subject area of a particular educational discipline.*

Keywords: *electronic educational resources, didactic content, formalization, axiomatic method, modeling.*

Introduction

Formalization of the meaning of the didactic content of knowledge of the subject area of educational disciplines in certain forms of concepts and statements carried out most often with the help of special formalized languages, methods and models. As the initial basis of such languages, authors usually use the axiomatic method, by means of which all known knowledge in a particular subject area

derived logically from a limited set of statements accepted as axioms [1, 2]. The interpretation of knowledge, in which the basic concepts expressed through axioms and have a well-defined meaning, we can call meaningful. Its final stage will be the derivation of theorems from axioms by transforming the original formulas according to the rules of logical inference, when signs and formulas of the symbolic language which we can use instead of theoretical statements. Such a system of formulas called an axiomatic model for formalizing the meaning of the didactic content of knowledge of the subject area of educational disciplines. At the same time, the operations of meaningful thinking displayed in this model by transforming formulas similar to calculations.

Main part

The axiomatic interpretation of the meaning of the didactic content of knowledge of the subject area of educational disciplines plays an important role in scientific knowledge. It allows: to systematize the didactic content of knowledge, presenting it in the form of conceptual systems; ensure the rigor of evidence, excluding recourse to implicit assumptions; identify and clarify the content of the didactic content of knowledge. However, it cannot fully reflect all the richness and diversity of developing knowledge.

We will show the possibilities of using axiomatic models to formalize the content of the didactic content of knowledge of the subject area of educational disciplines in the format of electronic educational resources (EER) [3, 4, 5, 6]. Today, there are no mechanisms for objective measurement of the “amount of knowledge” and reliable possibilities for determining the numerical values of the main parameters of this model. The existing dependencies between them can only be determined at a qualitative level with an accuracy of the ratio, while the dynamics of these dependencies detected at the level of trends.

The following will provide the axiomatic basis of our study:

1. There is some N -dimensional information space IP ($N \rightarrow \infty$), each i -th axis of which ($i=1, N$) IP_i corresponds to the didactic content of knowledge in the discipline D_i , ($i=1, N$);

2. The amount of didactic content of knowledge possessed by some j -th student, displayed in the N -dimensional space IP by the point $IP_j = \langle q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots, q_{ji}, \dots, q_{jN} \rangle$, where q_{ji} – point projection IP_j per axle IP_i ;

3. Each i -th axis ($i=1, N$) IP_i has a quantitative non-negative scale of values, that is each point q_i on the i -th axis corresponds to a specific amount of didactic content of knowledge in discipline D_i . In particular, the value $q_{ji} = 0$ means that the j -th student has no knowledge of discipline D_i , and the value $q_{ji} \neq 0$ means that j -th student has a certain amount of didactic content of knowledge on discipline D_i in the amount of q_{ji} .

4. The amount of knowledge Q_j^* , possessed by the j -th student, functionally depends on the values of all coordinates of the point IP_j over a distance IP :

$$Q_j^* = Q(q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots, q_{ji}, \dots, q_{jN}). \quad (1)$$

In the case when the j -th student has no knowledge of some disciplines $d_i (i=1, N)$, expression (1) will take form

$$Q_j^* = Q(q_{j1}, \dots, q_{ji-1}, 0, q_{ji+1}, \dots, q_{jN}). \quad (2)$$

Point IP_j , which has the dimension N , is an ideal reflection of the volume of the didactic content of knowledge of the j -th student, but it has a very limited applied value. Almost infinite ($N \rightarrow \infty$) dimension of the IP information space reflects reality, since it is impossible to determine an absolutely complete set of disciplines $D = \{d_i\} (i=1, N)$, knowledge of which a particular student has. For this reason, in pedagogical practice usually used a more simplified view of the knowledge of students. It is associated with fixing a set of disciplines, the study of which considered necessary for the qualification characteristics of students at each stage of their education in universities.

Obviously, for the entire learning process in the specialty S_l the boundaries of this truncated set of didactic knowledge content are determined by the number of K_l disciplines $D_l = \{d_{lk}\} (k=1, K_l)$, fixed in the curriculum u_l . Knowledge in disciplines (D^-), not included in the curriculum u_l , considered insignificant for the final qualification characteristics of students in the l -th specialty, and the amount of didactic content of knowledge in these disciplines is considered to be 0 by default. For each individual i -th, ($i=1, n_l$) stage of learning, the boundaries of an even more truncated set of didactic content of knowledge are determined by the list of disciplines studied at this stage $D_{il} = \{d_{ilh}\} (h=1, H_{il})$, while for a specific PO_{lmih} training stage, this list narrows down to a single discipline $d_{ilh} \in Dil$.

Thus, in the practice of teaching, the method of narrowing the set of didactic content of knowledge is used, which is taken into account when determining the qualification characteristics of trainees. It leads to the replacement of the complete set of didactic knowledge content possessed by the learner with a limited subset of didactic knowledge content in a finite set of disciplines defined by the curriculum ul . In particular, for a single stage of learning PO_{lmih} the volume of didactic content of knowledge in a single discipline $d_{ilh} \in D_{il}$, and for the i -th stage of training, the volume of didactic content of knowledge in all disciplines studied at this stage $D_{il} = \{d_{ilh}\} (h=1, H_{il})$. Exactly this representation further considers as an axiomatic model of the didactic content of the student's knowledge.

The model of the didactic content of the knowledge of the j -th student at the time of the beginning of his training in the specialty IPS_{jOul} is a set of knowledge that he mastered over the period of time preceding the start of training in the specialty S_l .

The dimension of this mode $N(IPS_{jOul})$ characterized by a small number of disciplines, and the procedure for assessing the volume of the didactic content of the student's knowledge is most often carried out in the form of entrance tests.

The model of the didactic content of the knowledge of the j -th student at the time of his graduation in the specialty IPS_{jOkl} is a set of knowledge that he mastered in the process of learning in the specialty Pl . The dimension of this model $N(IPS_{jOkl})$ characterized by a list of disciplines required for study according to the curriculum u_l .

If we group the set of disciplines $D = \{di\}$ ($i=1, N$) in the form

$$D = D_l \cup D' = \{d_{l1}, d_{l2}, \dots, d_{lK_l}, d_{lK_l+1}, \dots, d_{lN}\}, \quad (3)$$

And the dimension K_l knowledge model of a specific j -th student by some curriculum u_l at some point of time denote IP_{jOl} , then the volume of the didactic content of knowledge contained in this model can be represented by the expression:

$$Q_j = Q(q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots, q_{lK_l}, \dots, 0), \quad (4)$$

which is equivalent to the expression

$$Q_j = Q(q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots, q_{lK_l}). \quad (5)$$

It is obvious that the value of Q_j will always be less than the true "sum of knowledge" of the j -th student $Q_j^* = Q(q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots, q_{ji}, \dots, q_{jN})$. Since in the period preceding the formal fixation of the coordinate values q_{jk} ($k=1, K_l$), in addition to the disciplines to be studied according to the curriculum u_l , also accumulated other knowledge not directly related to training in the l -th specialty.

Let us consider at a qualitative level the dynamics of changes in the model of the didactic content of the student's knowledge in the next cycle PO_{lm} of training in the l -th specialty, taking into account the above decomposition of this process into stages and steps. Let us denote Q_{jul} as the volume of the didactic content of knowledge contained in the IP_{jOkl} knowledge of j -th student at the time of the beginning of the learning process PO_j :

$$Q_{jul} = Q(q_{ju1}, q_{ju2}, \dots, q_{juK_l}), \quad (6)$$

where q_{juk} ($k=1, K_l$) – the initial volume of didactic content of knowledge in the discipline $d_{lk} \in D_l$.

Obviously, for some disciplines of the curriculum u_l (which were not previously studied by the j -th student), the initial volume of didactic content of knowledge can be equal to 0, i.e.

$$q_{juk} = 0 \quad (k'=1, K_l) \quad (7)$$

In the process of implementing each cycle PO_{lm} of training in the l -th specialty, the initial model IP_{jOkl} replenished with volumes of didactic content of knowledge in the disciplines of this cycle $D_l = \{d_{lk}\}$ ($k=1, K_l$). At the same time, the learning cycle PO_{lm} structurally decomposed into nl sequentially executed stages P_{lmi} ($i=1, n$), each of which subdivided into H_{il} parallel stages PO_{lmih} , so the replenishment of the IP_{jOkl} model also has a serial-parallel character.

If the set of knowledge on the discipline studied at the stage PO_{lmih} discipline $d_{lih} \in D_l$ denote as IP_{lih} , then the change in the didactic content model of knowledge of the j -th student upon completion of this stage can be represented as

$$IP_{jOkI}(t_{iklm}) = IP_{jOkI}(t_{iulm}) \cup IP_{lih}, \quad (8)$$

where t_{iulm} and t_{iklm} – moments of the beginning and end of the i -th stage of the m -th cycle of training in the l -th specialty.

Let us assume that the initial volume of the didactic content of knowledge of the j -th student in the discipline $d_{lih} \in D_l$ is q_{jih} , its increment because of studying this discipline is equal to q_{lih} , and the discipline d_{lih} studied only during the i -th stage. Then the volume of the didactic content of knowledge contained in the knowledge model IP_{jOkI} of the j -th student knowledge after the completion of the stage PO_{lmih} , should increase by q_{lih} and amount to

$$Q_{jkl}(t_{iklm}) = Q_{jul}(t_{iulm}) \oplus q_{lih} = Q(q_{ju1}, q_{ju2}, \dots, q_{juh} + q_{lih}, \dots, q_{juKl}), \quad (9)$$

where $\oplus$ denotes the operation of adding knowledge to the model IP_{jOkI} .

Accordingly, upon completion of the i -th stage of learning PO_{lmi} , at which H_{il} disciplines $D_{il} = \{d_{ilh}\}$ studied in parallel, the knowledge model of the j -th student should be replenished with volumes of didactic content of knowledge in all disciplines studied at this stage $d_{lih} \in D_{il}$, that is

$$IP_{jOkI}(t_{iklm}) = IP_{jOkI}(t_{iulm}) \cup IP_{lih} \quad \forall (h=1, H_{il}). \quad (10)$$

The volumes of the didactic content of knowledge of the j -th student in the disciplines $d_{lih1}, d_{lih2}, \dots, d_{lihH}$ at the beginning of the i -th stage of training were respectively $q_{jih1}, q_{jih2}, \dots, q_{jihH}$, and their increments as a result studies of these disciplines are equal to $q_{lih1}, q_{lih2}, \dots, q_{lihH}$. Then upon completion of the i -th stage, the volume of the didactic content of knowledge contained in the IP_{jOkI} model should be

$$Q_{jkl}(t_{iklm}) = Q_{jul}(t_{iulm}) \oplus q_{lih1} \oplus q_{lih2} \oplus \dots \oplus q_{lihH} = \\ = Q(q_{ju1}, q_{ju2}, \dots, q_{juh1} + q_{lih1}, q_{juh2} + q_{lih2}, \dots, q_{juhH} + q_{lihH}, q_{juKl}). \quad (11)$$

Since all the stages PO_{lmih} ($h=1, H_{li}$) carried out on the same time interval $[t_{iulm}, t_{iklm}]$, it can be argued that within each individual i -th stage, the model of didactic content of knowledge IP_{jOkI} simultaneously replenished with volumes of knowledge in disciplines $d_{lih} \in D_{il}$ ($h=1, H_{il}$).

When implementing the m -th cycle of the learning process PO_{lm} in the l -th specialty, the didactic knowledge content model IP_{jOkI} j -th student consistently replenished with the amount of knowledge acquired at each of the n_l stages.

$$IP_{jOkI}(t_{klm}) = (((IP_{jOkI}(t_{ulm}) \cup IP_{11h}) \cup IP_{12h}) \dots \cup IP_{ln1h}) \\ \forall (h=1, H_{1l}), \forall (h=1, H_{2l}), \dots, \forall (h=1, H_{n1l}), \quad (12)$$

or in a more compact form

$$IP_{jOkI}(t_{klm}) = IP_{jOkI}(t_{ulm}) \cup \cup IP_{lih} \quad \forall (i=1, n_l), \forall (h=1, H_{il}). \quad (13)$$

In pedagogical practice, the situation is widespread when one discipline studied over several successive stages. Let the discipline $d_{lk} \in D_l$ made at the i -th, $(i+1)$ -th, ..., $(i+r)$ -th stages, it is decomposed into separate topics and (or) sections:

$$d_{lk} = d_{lihi} \cup d_{l(i+1)hi+1} \cup \dots \cup d_{l(i+r)hi+r}. \quad (14)$$

In this case, by analogy with (8) and (9), the sequential increment in the volume model of the didactic content of knowledge IP_{jOkI} from the moment t_{iulm} of the begin-

ning of the study of the discipline at the i -th stage and until the moment $t_{(i+r)klm}$ of the completion of its study can be expressed

$$IP_{jOkI}(t_{(i+r)klm}) = IP_{jOkI}(t_{iilm}) \cup IP_{l(i+1)hi+1} \cup \dots \cup IP_{l(i+r)hi+r}, \quad (15)$$

and the amount of didactic content of knowledge contained in the IP_{jOkI} model at the end of the $(i+r)$ -th stage of training should be

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{jkl}(t_{(i+r)klm}) &= Q_{jul}(t_{iilm}) \oplus q_{lihi} \oplus q_{l(i+1)hi+1} \oplus \dots \oplus q_{l(i+r)hi+r} = \\ &= Q(q_{ju1}, q_{ju2}, \dots, q_{juh} + q_{lihi} + q_{l(i+1)hi+1} + \dots + q_{l(i+r)hi+r}, \dots, q_{j'kl}). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Expressions (15) and (16) easily generalized to the case of studying an arbitrary number of disciplines at several stages.

Conclusion

Thus, usage of axiomatic models allows us to present in a formalized form not only the content of the didactic content of knowledge of the subject area in the context of specific educational disciplines, but also their interpretation in the form of certain concepts and statements. On this basis, it is quite easy to form a model of the didactic content of students' knowledge and track the dynamics of its change in the learning process. Thus, the inclusion of EER, containing various amounts of didactic content of knowledge in individual disciplines, achieved in the information and educational environment of the university to manage the educational process and assess the level of knowledge of each student. This approach puts into practice the principle of student-centered learning based on the use of EER.

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